

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
COMPUTER GRAPHICS SYSTEM PROJECT
REPORT
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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

Computer graphics is one of the most exciting and rapidly growing computer fields. It is also an extremely effective medium for communication between man and computer; a human being can understand the information content of a displayed diagram or perspective view much faster than he can understand a table of numbers or text containing the same information. Thus, computer graphics is being used more extensively.

There is a lot of development in hardware and software required to generate images, and nowadays the cost of such hardware and software is dropping rapidly. Due to this the interactive computer graphics is becoming available to more and more people.

Computer graphics started with the display of data on hardcopy plotters and cathode ray tube (CRT) screens soon after the introduction of computers themselves. It has grown to include the creation, storage, and manipulation of models and images of objects. These models come from a diverse and expanding set of fields, and include physical, mathematical, engineering, architectural, and even conceptual structures, natural phenomena, and so on.

Computer graphics today is largely interactive. The user controls the contents, structure, and appearance of objects and their displayed images by using input devices, such as a keyboard, mouse, or touch sensitive panel on the screen. The handling of such devices is included in the study of computer graphics, because of the close relationship between the input devices and the display.

1.2 About C:

'C' seems a strange name for a programming language. But this strange sounding language is one of the most popular computer languages today. C is an offspring of 'Basic Combined Programming Language' (BPCL) called B, developed in 1960's at Cambridge University. B language was modified by Dennis Ritchie and was implemented in Bell laboratories in 1972. This new language was named C.

'C++' has its origin in C language. It was developed by Bjarne Stroustrup at AT&T Bell labs in the early 1980's to overcome the shortcomings of C. Initially named 'C with classes', the language is actually improved version of C language with some additional features made possible by using classes and an object-oriented approach.

1.3 Important Features of C/C++

The following are the most important features of C/C++

1.3.1. Simple

1.3.2. Object oriented (C++)

1.3.3 Robust

1.3.4 Rich set of built in programs and operations

1.3.5 Programs written are efficient and fast.

1.3.6 Highly portable.

1.3.7 Ability to extend itself.

1.4 Graphics Support in C/C++:

One of the most important features of C/C++ is its ability to draw graphics. We can write C/C++ graphics programs to draw figures of different shapes, images and text in different forms and styles. It has a rich set of built in functions and operations in the basic graphical interface

(BGI). All interfaces to the SRGP and SPHIGS graphics package are defined in C/C++.

The objective of this project is to design and implement a paint editor similar to the MS-PAINT application. We use our computer graphics skills to create this application by operating on C in 'graphics' mode.

C/C++ co-ordinate system has a origin (0,0) in the upper-left corner. Positive x values are to the right, and positive y values are to the bottom. The values of the coordinates x and y are in pixels.

1.5 Co-ordinate System

2. REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATIONS

Purpose: The purpose of this document is to describe all external requirements for designing a graphics package called Paint.

Scope: This document describes the functional requirements for the graphics package to run efficiently and provide optimum results. It is meant for use by the developers and will also be used for further maintaining and upgrading the various components of the requirements in future. Then, it will be reflected as an addition to this document.

2.1 User characteristics:

2.1.1. User should be proficient in C/C++ and Windows environment.

2.1.2. User should know to compile and run files in C/C++.

2.2 Software Requirements:

2.2.1. Platform: DOS/Windows family

2.2.2. Software Tools: C++ Compiler

2.3 Hardware Requirements:

2.3.1. Pentium processor-III/IV

2.3.2. Max:4 GB Disk Drive.

2.3.3. Input devices-Mouse and Keyboard.

2.3.4. IBM compatible PC.

2.3.5. RGB 256 colours-Video minimum 16 colours and 640x480 resolutions.

2.3.6. 32 MB RAM.

2. 4 Features of the project:

The graphics package supports interaction with mouse through menus for the users to implement various options such as

- 2.4.1. Drawing a line
- 2.4.2. Drawing a circle
- 2.4.3. Drawing an ellipse
- 2.4.4. Drawing a rectangle
- 2.4.5. Drawing a spiral
- 2.4.6. Rotating wheel
- 2.4.7. Moving line around circle
- 2.4.8. Translation of rectangle
- 2.4.9. Rotation of rectangle
- 2.4.10. Scaling of rectangle
- 2.4.11. 3D transformations on rectangle
- 2.4.12. Segmentation
- 2.4.13. Clipping outside region of a selected area
- 2.4.14. Creating a new file
- 2.4.15. Saving the current file
- 2.4.16. Loading an old file
- 2.4.17. Filling entire area with selected colour
- 2.4.18. Displays the current mouse position

3. SYSTEM DESIGN

The objective of this particular design is to implement the graphics project called Paint in an efficient way. It is designed using many built-in functions and also user-defined functions. This increases the speed and efficiency.

3.1 Design Methodology

3.1.1 Mouse Interfacing

We use the following functions to interface the mouse with the user screen.

`void showmouse()`

This is a function which displays mouse position on the screen. It is called using service 01h and has no return value. It uses interrupt 33h.

`void hidemouse()`

This is a function which hides the mouse pointer on the screen. It is called using service 02h and has no return value. It uses interrupt 33h.

`Int getmousepos()`

This is a function which gets the current mouse pointer on the screen. It is called using service 03h. This returns mouse button status to BX and x-coordinate to CX and y-coordinate to DX . It uses interrupt 33h.

int restrictmouse()

This is a function which sets the horizontal and vertical limits for pointer. Horizontal limit is set using service 07h. Register CX contains minimum x-coordinate and DX contains maximum x-coordinate. Vertical limit is set using service 08h. Register CX contains minimum y-coordinate and DX contains maximum y-coordinate.

3.12 Other Features

Line: We can draw a line in any of the coordinates using Bresenham's line algorithm. Based on the input values given by the user, slopes are calculated and corresponding pixels are called using putpixel() built-in function. We also ensure that the line lies within the user area.

Rectangle: We can draw a rectangle using service 03h, which returns current x and y coordinates. Then, we call line function 4 times to draw a rectangle and ensure that it is within user area as long as left button is pressed.

Circle: We can draw a circle using Bresenham's circle algorithm. The initial left click position of the mouse is taken as the centre of the circle. The radius is given by service 03h which returns x and y coordinates when the left button is released. We ensure that it is within the user area.

Ellipse: We can draw an ellipse using modified Bresenham's algorithm. An ellipse of any major and minor axis may be drawn. We ensure that it is within the user area.

Spiral: We can draw a spiral using service 02h. It makes use of contents of CX and DX registers to know the centre and maximum radius. We ensure that it is within the user area.

Clip-out: We can clip objects outside a selected area. We use Cohen Sutherland method of clipping.

Wheel: When this icon is clicked, a rotating wheel is displayed within the user screen, until right button of mouse is clicked.

Rotating tangent: When this icon is clicked, a tangent moves around a circle until keyboard is hit.

Translate: We can translate a given circle within the user screen. The circle is translated to the position where the mouse is clicked.

New file: We can create a new file by filling the entire user area with white colour and naming it as untitled.bmp.

Save file: We can save a created image by using file operations.

Load file: We can load a saved file by using file operations. If the file is not present, error is displayed.

Segmentation: When this icon is clicked, the segmentation program output is displayed.

Clear: This option clears the screen and fills the user area with white colour.

Colours: We can select a colour and perform any of the operations using that colour.

Fill colour: This option fills the entire user screen within the selected colour.

Locator position: It displays the coordinate position of the mouse Pointer.

Most graphics editors use the following screed design.

The construction techniques are one of the most important ingredients of a graphics editor. A superior approach to the construction technique is the rubber-band technique, which is used in this editor. The state diagram for rubber-band line drawing is show below.

Source Code

```
/* GLOBAL DECLARATION
*/

#include<stdio.h>
#include<dos.h>
#include<graphics.h>
#include<conio.h>
#include<stdlib.h>
#include<math.h>
#include<time.h>

#define MIN_X 100
#define MAX_X 627
#define MIN_Y 70
#define MAX_Y 390
#define MAX_BUTTONS 25
#define MAX_COLOR 16 //total no of color buttons
#define NEW 0
#define SAVE 1
#define LOAD 2
#define CLEAR 3
#define CLIP_OP 10
#define TRANS_OP 19
#define MAX_PIXEL 5000
#define ORG -50
#define PI 3.1415927
#define M 5

void wel();
int initmouse();
void startmouse(int x,int y);
void showmouse();
void hidemouse();
void getxy();
void disp_coord();
void restrictmouse(int,int,int,int);
void tme();

void ClearStatus();
void ShowStatus(char*);
void beep();
char* readline(char*);
void animate();
//void loading();
void save();
void load();
void clear();
void exchange(int*,int*);
```

```
//void erase();

void drawtext();
void putback();
void set(int x,int y);

void putcircle(int,int,int,int);
void bcircle( int,int,int);
void setpixel(int,int,int);
void bline(int,int,int,int);
void brectangle(int,int,int,int);
void spiral(int,int,int,int,int);
void plotpnts(int,int,int,int,int,int);
void bellipse(int,int,int,int);
void myw(int,int,float);
void Wheel();
void myl(int,int,float);
void rotate_line();
void rubberband();
void scale();
void rotate();
void translate();
void
CohenSutherlandLine(int,int,int,int,int,int,int,int);
void lineclipping();
void clearin();
void clearout();
void seg();

void New_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Save_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Open_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Line_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Rectangle_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Circle_icon(int x1, int y1);
void Ellipse_icon(int x2,int y1);
void Spiral_icon(int x1,int y1);
void Rot_icon(int x1,int y1);
void Rotate_icon(int x, int y);
void Translate_icon(int x1, int y1);
void scale_icon(int x1,int y1);
void Clip_icon(int x1,int y1);
void Wheel_icon(int x2,int y1);
void Seg_icon(int x1,int y1);
void icons(int,int,int,int,int);
void init_button(int,int,int,int,int,int,char*);
void draw_button_border(int);
void undraw_button_border(int);
void init_color_button(int,int,int,int,int);
void draw_color_button_border(int);
void init();
```

```
void dispfile();
void frame();
int check_mouse_on(int,int,int,int);
void check_if_exit();
int check_if_color();
int check_if_button_pressed();
void tools();
void drawrectangle();

int a,b,c,d;
int Current_Color=BLACK;
int Current_Pattern=EMPTY_FILL;

struct          //the button-structure consists of
{
    int xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax;    //1.boundaries-field
    int button_no;              //2.the button-no. for
access
    char* desc;                  //3.a string for
description to the user
}buttons[MAX_BUTTONS];

struct          //another structure-this time for color-
buttons
{
    //consists of:
    int xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax;    //1.boundaries-fields
    int color;                  //2.color-i.e. color no.
}colorbuttons[MAX_COLOR];

struct
{
    int x,y;
    int c;
}r[MAX_PIXEL];
struct Node
{
    int x,y;
    struct Node* next;
};

int R; //restore mode
int t; //number of pixel to restore
char filename[20]="Untitled";
int saved;
int LeftButtonPressed; //is leftbutton-pressed
int RightButtonPressed; // is Right button pressed
int mousex,mousey; //current mouse pos
int prevx,prevy; //prev mouse pos
//int Current_Color=BLACK; // to Store the current color
int Current_Button=9; // to store the current button
pressed
```

```

int Prev_Button=1;// to store the previous button
union REGS regs;

void wel()
{

}

/*          INITIALISE THE SCREEN
*/
void frame()
{
    char name[20];
    setcolor(WHITE);
    rectangle(3,3,637,477);
    setfillstyle(1,10);
    floodfill(6,6,WHITE);
    icons(10,70,93,455,0);    // icon button panel
    icons(MIN_X+1,MIN_Y+1,MAX_X-1,MAX_Y-1,0);
    icons(MIN_X-1,MIN_Y-1,MAX_X+1,MAX_Y+1,1);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL, WHITE);
    bar(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-2,MAX_Y-2);    //drawing
screen
    icons(10,460,629-200,477-3,0);    //help message
panel(status display)
    icons(20,MAX_Y+50,83,MAX_Y+60,0);
    icons(629-200+32,460,MAX_X-34,477-3,0); //for x y
display_panel
    setcolor(BLACK);
    outtextxy(467,464,"x :");
    outtextxy(533,464,"y :");
    icons(MIN_X+70,MAX_Y+25,MIN_X+75+2+240,MAX_Y+65,1); //
For color panel
    setcolor(DARKGRAY);
    icons(MIN_X+15,MAX_Y+30,MIN_X+49,MAX_Y+55,1); //for
current_Color_indicator
    icons(MIN_X+16,MAX_Y+31,MIN_X+48,MAX_Y+55,1);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,Current_Color);
    bar(MIN_X+15+5,MAX_Y+35,MIN_X+49-5,MAX_Y+50);
    setcolor(WHITE);
    line(3,35,637,35);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,BLUE);floodfill(630,30,WHITE);
    setcolor(4);
    settextstyle(7,HORIZ_DIR,2);
    outtextxy((getmaxx()-textwidth("    2DPACKAGE
"))/2,7,"    2DPACKAGE");
    settextstyle(SMALL_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,4);
    setcolor(4);
    outtextxy(438,417,"Designed by : ");
    settextstyle(SMALL_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,4);
    settextstyle(4,0,1);

```

```
    outtextxy(430,432,"chinmaya \n amar");
    settextstyle (SMALL_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,5);
    icons(MAX_X-208,MAX_Y+25,MAX_X-2,MAX_Y+65,1);
    icons(MIN_X,MAX_Y+6,MAX_X,MAX_Y+18,0);

}

void New_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to show new file
icon
{
    y1+=1;
    setlinestyle(0,1,1);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    line(9+x1,4+y1,9+x1,20+y1);
    line(9+x1,20+y1,21+x1,20+y1);
    line(21+x1,20+y1,21+x1,8+y1);
    line(9+x1,4+y1,17+x1,4+y1);
    line(17+x1,4+y1,17+x1,8+y1);
    line(17+x1,8+y1,21+x1,8+y1);
    line(21+x1,8+y1,17+x1,4+y1);
    setfillstyle(1,WHITE);
    floodfill(10+x1,9+y1,BLACK);
}

void Save_icon(int x1, int y1) // for saving
{
    y1+=1;
    setlinestyle(0,1,1);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    line(6+x1,4+y1,24+x1,4+y1);
    line(24+x1,4+y1,24+x1,20+y1);
    line(24+x1,20+y1,8+x1,20+y1);
    line(8+x1,20+y1,6+x1,18+y1);
    line(6+x1,18+y1,6+x1,4+y1);
    line(9+x1,4+y1,9+x1,12+y1);
    line(9+x1,12+y1,21+x1,12+y1);
    line(21+x1,12+y1,21+x1,4+y1);
    line(10+x1,20+y1,10+x1,15+y1);
    line(10+x1,15+y1,20+x1,15+y1);
    line(20+x1,15+y1,20+x1,20+y1);
    line(17+x1,15+y1,17+x1,20+y1);
    line(21+x1,7+y1,24+x1,7+y1);
    setfillstyle(1,WHITE);
    floodfill(10+x1,5+y1,BLACK);
    setfillstyle(1,BROWN);
    floodfill(7+x1,5+y1,BLACK);
    setfillstyle(1,DARKGRAY);
    floodfill(11+x1,19+y1,BLACK);
}
```

```
void Open_icon(int x1, int y1)// for opening
{
    y1+=1;
    setlinestyle(0,1,1);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    line(5+x1,20+y1,17+x1,20+y1);
    line(17+x1,20+y1,24+x1,15+y1);
    line(24+x1,15+y1,12+x1,15+y1);
    line(12+x1,15+y1,5+x1,20+y1);
    setfillstyle(1,DARKGRAY);
    floodfill(10+x1,18+y1,BLACK);
    line(5+x1,20+y1,5+x1,10+y1);
    line(5+x1,10+y1,6+x1,8+y1);
    line(6+x1,8+y1,8+x1,8+y1);
    line(8+x1,8+y1,9+x1,10+y1);
    line(9+x1,10+y1,17+x1,10+y1);
    line(17+x1,10+y1,17+x1,15+y1);
    setfillstyle(1,YELLOW);
    floodfill(6+x1,12+y1,BLACK);
    line(15+x1,7+y1,17+x1,5+y1);
    line(17+x1,5+y1,22+x1,7+y1);
    line(22+x1,7+y1,24+x1,12+y1);
    line(24+x1,12+y1,20+x1,10+y1);
    line(24+x1,12+y1,26+x1,9+y1);
}

void Clear_icon(int x,int y)//clearing the working area
{
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,WHITE);
    bar3d(x+5,y+5,x+25,y+20,0,0);
}

void Line_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to show line icon
{
    line(x1+8,y1+5,x1+22,y1+19);
    line(x1+7,y1+4,x1+21,y1+18);
}

void Circle_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to show circle
icon
{
    circle(x1+15,y1+13,8);
}

void Ellipse_icon(int x2,int y1)//used to show ellipse
tool
{
    ellipse(x2+15,y1+13,0,360,10,7);
}
```

```
void Spiral_icon(int x1,int y1) //used to show spiral
icon
{
    setcolor(BLACK);
    spiral(x1+15,y1+14,10,0,37);
}
void Rot_icon(int x1,int y1)//used to show rotate icon
{
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,YELLOW);
    circle(x1+15,y1+13,7);
    line(x1+23,y1+5,x1+23,y1+21);
}

void Clip_icon(int x1,int y1)//used to display line
clipping
{
    setlinestyle(3,0,2);
    rectangle(x1+6,y1+6,x1+24,y1+19);
    setlinestyle(0,0,0);
    line(x1+20,y1+3,x1+10,y1+23);
}

void Wheel_icon(int x2,int y1) //used to show moving
wheel
{
    circle(x2+15,y1+13,8);
    circle(x2+15,y1+13,10);
    line(x2+7,y1+13,x2+23,y1+13);
    line(x2+15,y1+5,x2+15,y1+21);
    line(x2+9,y1+7,x2+21,y1+19);
    line(x2+21,y1+7,x2+9,y1+19);
}

void Seg_icon(int x,int y)
{
    setcolor(4);
    setttextstyle(DEFAULT_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,0);
    outtextxy(x+4,y+9,"SEG");
}

void hr_icon(int x,int y)
{
    setcolor(4);
    setttextstyle(1,0,1);
    outtextxy(x+8,y+10,"HR");
}

void bz_icon(int x,int y)
{
    setcolor(RED);
```

```
        settextstyle(1,0,1);
        outtextxy(x+8,y+10,"BZ");
    }

void t3d_icon(int x,int y)
{
    setcolor(RED);
    settextstyle(1,0,1);
    outtextxy(x+8,y+10,"3D");
}

void fl_icon(int x,int y)
{
    setcolor(RED);
    settextstyle(1,0,1);
    outtextxy(x+4,y+10,"FIL");
}

void Rotate_icon(int x, int y)
{
    setcolor(0);
    rectangle(x+6,y+4,x+23,y+18);
    setcolor(RED);
    line(x+11,y+4,x+6,y+18);
    line(x+11,y+4,x+27,y+9);
    line(x+27,y+9,x+22,y+22);
    line(x+22,y+22,x+6,y+18);
}

void Rectangle_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to show
rectangle icon
{
    rectangle(x1+6,y1+6,x1+23,y1+20);
}

void Translate_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to display
translation
{
    setcolor(0);
    rectangle(x1+4,y1+4,x1+21,y1+18);
    setcolor(RED);
    rectangle(x1+7,y1+7,x1+24,y1+21);
}

void scale_icon(int x1, int y1)// used to display
scaling picture
{
    setcolor(0);
    rectangle(x1+4,y1+4,x1+21,y1+18);
    rectangle(x1+7,y1+7,x1+17,y1+12);
}
```

```
        setfillstyle(1,RED);
        floodfill(x1+8,y1+8,BLACK);
    }

    /*                      MOUSE FUNCTIONS
       */

    int initmouse()
    {
        regs.x.ax=0;
        int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
        return(regs.x.bx);
    }

    void startmouse(int x,int y) //start mouse in pos(x,y)
    using                      //fn. 04h of int 33h
    {
        regs.x.ax=4;
        regs.x.cx=x;
        regs.x.dx=y;
        int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
    }

    void showmouse()
    {
        regs.x.ax=1;
        int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
    }

    void getxy()
    {
        regs.x.ax=3;                      //get mouse status using 03h
    of int 33h
        int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
        prevx=mousex;
        prevy=mousey;
        if(regs.x.bx&1)                    //LSB of reg BX
            LeftButtonPressed=1;
        else
            LeftButtonPressed=0;
        mousex=regs.x.cx;                  //(cx,dx)=(x,y)
        mousey=regs.x.dx;
        if(regs.x.bx&2)
            RightButtonPressed=1;
        else
            RightButtonPressed=0;
    }

    void hidemouse()
```

```

{
    regs.x.ax=2;
    int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
}

void disp_coord() //this fn display current mouse co-
ordinates only when
{
    //the mouse is on the canvas
    char x[5],y[5];
    int color;
    if(prevx!=mousex||prevy!=mousey)
        //otherwise don't update
        if((mousex>MIN_X+1)&&(mousex<MAX_X-
1)&&(mousey>MIN_Y+1)&&(mousey<MAX_Y-1))
        {
            settxtstyle(DEFAULT_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,0); //restore
normal font style/size
            sprintf(x," %d ",mousex-MIN_X-2); //copy positions
into respective
            sprintf(y," %d ",mousey-MIN_Y-2); //strings
            color=getcolor();
            setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
            bar(487,462,522,472); //refresh display
            bar(555,462,585,472);
            setcolor(BLACK);
            outtextxy(487,464,x); //display
current positions
            outtextxy(555,464,y);
            setcolor(color);
        }
}

void restrictmouse(int minx,int miny,int maxx,int maxy)
{
    regs.x.cx=minx;
    regs.x.dx=maxx;
    regs.x.ax=0x7; //restrict along x-axis using fn
07h
    int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
    regs.x.cx=miny;
    regs.x.dx=maxy;
    regs.x.ax=0x8; //restrict along y-axis using fn
08h
    int86(0x33,&regs,&regs);
}
//Time function

void tme()
{
    char k[3],l[3],m[4]=" : ";
    static int hour,minute;

```

```

regs.h.ah=0x2c;
int86(0x21,&regs,&regs);
if(hour!=regs.h.ch||minute!=regs.h.cl)
{
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
    bar(22,MAX_Y+52,81,MAX_Y+58);           //refresh
display
    settextstyle(DEFAULT_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,0); //restore
normal font    style/size
    //setusercharsize(0,0,0,0);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    sprintf(k,"%d",regs.h.ch);
    outtextxy(25,442,k);
    outtextxy(40,442,m);
    sprintf(l,"%d",regs.h.cl);
    outtextxy(62,442,l);
}
hour=regs.h.ch,minute=regs.h.cl;
}

/*          FILE OPERATIONS
*/

extern void dispfile();
void ClearStatus()
{
    static int first_time;
    static char text[52];
    int i;
    setcolor(LIGHTGRAY);
    if(!first_time)
    {
        strcpy(text,"");
        for(i=0;i<51;++i)
            strcat(text,"U");
        text[51]='\0';
        first_time=1;
    }
    outtextxy(12,464,text);
}

void ShowStatus(char* str)
{
    int color=getcolor();
    ClearStatus();
    setcolor(BLACK);
    outtextxy(32,464,str);
    setcolor(color);
}

```

```
void beep()
{
    sound(1000);
    delay(75);
    nosound();
}

char* readline(char* msg)
{
    char* Line;
    char temp[40];
    char Disp_Line[60];
    char ch;
    int i=0,length=0;
    int max=((475-12)-strlen(msg)*8)/8;// find maximum
number of characters
    ClearStatus();
    setcolor(BLACK);
    outtextxy(12,464,msg);
    strcpy(Disp_Line,msg);
    ch=getch();
    while((ch!=27)&&(ch!=13))
    {
        switch (ch)
        {
            case '\b' :
                if(i==0)
                    beep();
                else
                {
                    i--;
                    ClearStatus();
                    length=strlen(Disp_Line);
                    Disp_Line[length-1]='\0';
                    setcolor(BLACK);
                    outtextxy(12,464,Disp_Line);
                }
                break;
            default :
                if(i > max)
                    beep();
                else
                {
                    length=strlen(Disp_Line);
                    Disp_Line[length]=ch; //copy next char
into Disp_Line
                    Disp_Line[length+1]='\0';
                    outtextxy(12,464,Disp_Line);
                    temp[i++]=ch;
                }
                break;
        }
    }
}
```

```
    }
    ch=getch();
}
temp[i]='\0';
ClearStatus();
if(ch==27)
    return NULL;
else
{
    Line=malloc(strlen(temp)+1);
    strcpy(Line,temp);
}
return Line;
}
void animate()
{
    int i,j=2;
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,BLUE);
    for(i=1;i<66;i++)
    {
        bar(MIN_X+j,MAX_Y+15,MIN_X+j+6,MAX_Y+9);
        j+=8;
        delay(10);
    }
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
    bar(MIN_X+2,MAX_Y+16,626,MAX_Y+8);
}

void save()
{
    char* name;
    FILE* out;
    char ch;
    int row,col;
    char byte;
    if(strcmp(filename,"Untitled")==0)
    {
        name=readline("Save File As : ");
        if(name==NULL) return;
    }
    else
    {
        name=malloc(strlen(filename)+1);
        strcpy(name,filename);
    }
    out=fopen(name,"w");
    if(out==NULL)
    {
        ShowStatus(" Error Opening File !");
        delay(1000);
        ClearStatus();
    }
}
```

```
        return;
    }
    ShowStatus(" Saving File (Please Wait) ");
    animate();
    for(row=MIN_Y+2;row<=MAX_Y-2;++row)
    {
        for(col=MIN_X+2;col<=MAX_X-2;)
        {
            byte=getpixel(col,row);
            byte=byte<<4;
            col++;
            byte+=getpixel(col,row);
            col++;
            if(fputc(byte,out)==EOF)
            {
                ShowStatus("Error Writing File ! ");
                delay(1000);
                ClearStatus();
                free(name);
                fclose(out);
            }
        }
    }
    ClearStatus();
    strcpy(filename,name);
    dispfile();
    free(name);
    fclose(out);
    saved=1;
}

void load()
{
    FILE* in;
    char* name;
    char ch;
    char byte;
    int row,col;
    int temp;
    if(!saved)
    {
        ShowStatus(" Save Current File ? ");
        ch=getch();
        if(ch=='y' || ch=='Y')
            save();
    }
    name=readline(" Enter File To Open : ");
    if(name==NULL)
        return;
    in=fopen(name,"r");
    if(in==NULL)
```

```

    {
        ShowStatus(" Error Opening File ");
        delay(1000);
        ClearStatus();
        return;
    }
    byte=fgetc(in); // gets a char from a stream
    ClearStatus();
    ShowStatus("Loading....");
    animate();
    ClearStatus();
    strcpy(filename,name);
    dispfile();
    for(row=MIN_Y+2;row<=MAX_Y-2;row++)
    {
        for(col=MIN_X+2;col<=MAX_X-2;)
        {
            temp=(byte&0xf0)>>4;
            putpixel(col,row,temp);
            col++;
            temp=(byte&0x0f);
            putpixel(col,row,temp);
            col++;
            byte=fgetc(in);
        }
    }
    free(name);
    fclose(in);
    saved=1;
}

```

```

/*          ALGORITHMS
*/
void clear()
{
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,WHITE);
    bar(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-2,MAX_Y-2);
}

void exchange(int *v1,int *v2) // to swap variables in
line algo
{
    int temp;
    temp=*v1;
    *v1=*v2;
    *v2=temp;
}

```

```
void putback()
{
    int i;
    for(i=0;i<t;i++)
    {
        if(getpixel(r[i].x,r[i].y)!=r[i].c)
            putpixel(r[i].x,r[i].y,r[i].c);
    }
    t=0;
}

void set(int x,int y)
{
    if(x>MIN_X+1&& x<MAX_X-1&& y>MIN_Y+1&& y<MAX_Y-1)
    {
        if(getpixel(x,y)!=Current_Color)
        {
            if(R)
            {
                r[t].c=getpixel(x,y);
                r[t].x=x;
                r[t++].y=y;
            }
            putpixel(x,y,Current_Color);
        }
    }
}

void putcircle(int x,int y,int xc,int yc)
{
    set(x+xc,y+yc);
    set(-x+xc,y+yc);
    set(y+xc,-x+yc);
    set(-y+xc,x+yc);
    set(x+xc,-y+yc);
    set(-x+xc,-y+yc);
    set(y+xc,x+yc);
    set(-y+xc,-x+yc);
}

void bcircle( int xc,int yc,int rad)
{
    int x=0,y=rad,p=3-2*rad;
    if(rad<3)
        return;
    hidemouse();
    while(x<=y)
    {
        putcircle(x,y,xc,yc);
        if(p<0)
```

```
        p+=4*x+6;
        else
        {
        p+=4*(x-y)+10;
        y--;
        }
        x++;
        if(x==y)
        putcircle(x,y,xc,yc);
    }
    showmouse();
}

void setpixel(int x,int y,int slope)
{
    if(slope)
        exchange(&x,&y);
    set(x,y);
}

void bline(int xs,int ys,int xe,int ye)
{
    int dx,dy,c1,c2,slope,stype=1;
    signed long int p;
    dx=abs(xe-xs);
    dy=abs(ye-ys);
    slope=dy>dx;
    if(slope)
    {
        exchange(&dx,&dy);
        exchange(&xs,&ys);
        exchange(&xe,&ye);
    }
    c1=2*dy;  c2=2*(dy-dx);  p=2*dy-dx;
    if(xe<xs)
    {
        exchange(&xs,&xe);
        exchange(&ys,&ye);
    }
    if(ye<ys)
        stype=-1;
    setpixel(xs,ys,slope);
    while(xs<xe)
    {
        ++xs;
        if(p<0)
            p+=c1;
        else
        {
            p+=c2;
            ys+=stype;
        }
    }
}
```

```
        }
        setpixel(xs,ys,slope);
    }
}

void brectangle(int x1,int y1,int x2,int y2)
{
    hidemouse();
    if(x1==x2&&yl==y2)
    {
        showmouse();
        return;
    }
    bline(x1,y1,x2,y1);
    bline(x2,y1,x2,y2);
    bline(x2,y2,x1,y2);
    bline(x1,y1,x1,y2);
    showmouse();
}

void spiral(int xc,int yc,int r,int cip,int inc)
{
    int x1,y1,x2,y2;
    float theta,dtheta,rad;
    if(r<=5)
        return;
    x1=xc;
    y1=yc;
    theta=rad=0.0;
    dtheta=M_PI/(60);
    while(rad<=r)
    {
        x2=xc+rad*cos(theta);
        y2=yc+rad*sin(theta);
        if(cip)
            bline(x1,y1,x2,y2);
        else
            line(x1,y1,x2,y2); //for icon
        x1=x2;
        y1=y2;
        rad+=(0.1/inc)*r;
        theta+=dtheta;
    }
    return;
}

void plotpnts(int xc,int yc,int x,int y,int r1,int r2)
{
    float r=1.0,ro=1.0;
    if(r1>r2)
        r=(float)(r2*1.0/r1);
```

```
    else
        ro=(float) (r1*1.0/r2);
    set(xc+x*ro, (int) (yc+y*r));
    set(xc-y*ro, (int) (yc+x*r));
    set(xc-x*ro, (int) (yc+y*r));
    set(xc+y*ro, (int) (yc+x*r));

    set(xc-x*ro, (int) (yc-y*r));
    set(xc+y*ro, (int) (yc-x*r));
    set(xc+x*ro, (int) (yc-y*r));
    set(xc-y*ro, (int) (yc-x*r));
}

void bellipse(int xc,int yc,int r1,int r2)
{
    int p,x,y,b;
    x=0;
    if(r1>r2)
        y=r1;
    else
        y=r2;
    p=3-2*r1;
    while(x<=y)
    {
        hidemouse();
        plotpnts(xc,yc,x,y,r1,r2);
        showmouse();
        if(p<0)
            p+=4*x+6;
        else
        {
            y--;
            p+=4*(x-y)+10;
        }
        x++;
    }
    showmouse();
}

void myw(int x,int y,float theta)
{
    int i;
    circle(x,y,50);
    circle(x,y,48);
    for(i=0;i<3;i++)
    {
        line(x+50*cos(theta),y+50*sin(theta),x-
50*cos(theta),y-50*sin(theta));
        theta+=M_PI/3;
    }
}
```

```

void hrcurve(int x1,int y1,int x4,int y4)
{
    int x3,y3;
    double a,b,t,r1,r2;
    //x2=87,y2=47;
    //x3=632,y3=427;
    r1=abs(x4-x1);
    r2=abs(y4-y1);
    for(t=0;t<1;t+=0.001)
    {
        a=(2*t*t*t-3*t*t+1)*x1+(-2*t*t*t+3*t*t)*x4+(t*t*t-
2*t*t+t)*r1+(t*t*t-t*t)*r2;
        b=(2*t*t*t-3*t*t+1)*y1+(-2*t*t*t+3*t*t)*y4+(t*t*t-
2*t*t+1)*r1+(t*t*t-t*t)*r2;
        if((a>87&&a<632) && (b>47&&b<427))
            bline((int)a, (int)b, (int)a, (int)b);
    }
}

void bzcurve(int x1,int y1,int x4,int y4)
{
    int x3,y3,x2,y2;
    double a,b,t;
    x2=87,y2=47;
    x3=632,y3=427;
    for(t=0;t<1;t+=0.0001)
    {
        a=(1-t)*(1-t)*(1-t)*x1+3*t*(1-t)*(1-t)*x2+3*t*t*(1-
t)*x3+t*t*t*x4;
        b=(1-t)*(1-t)*(1-t)*y1+3*t*(1-t)*(1-t)*y2+3*t*t*(1-
t)*y3+t*t*t*y4;
        if((a>87&&a<632) && (b>47&&b<427))
            bline((int)a, (int)b, (int)a, (int)b);
    }
}

void rotate()
{
    char *name;
    int x,y,xnew=0,ynew=0;
    float tx=0,th=0;
    setcolor(Current_Color);
    rectangle(MIN_X,MIN_Y,MAX_X,MAX_Y);
    ShowStatus("Draw rectangle to rotate");
    drawrectangle();
    name=readline("Enter the rotational angle along x-
axis: ");
    tx=atoi(name);
    th= (3.1416 * tx)/180.0;
}

```

```

        for(x=MIN_X+2; x<=MAX_X-2; x++)
            for(y=MIN_Y+2; y<=MAX_Y-2; y++)
                if(getpixel(x,y) !=WHITE &&
getpixel(x,y)==BLACK)
                    {
                        xnew = ( ( x*cos(th) -
y*sin(th)) );
                        ynew = ( ( x*sin(th) +
y*cos(th)) );
                        //      if(xnew>100&&ynew<340)
putpixel(x,y,15);
                        putpixel(xnew+200,abs(ynew-
70),10);
                        continue;
                    }
    }
void seg()
{
setcolor(BLACK);

rectangle(200,200,400,380);
line(200,200,300,100);
line(300,100,400,200);
rectangle(275,300,325,380);
rectangle(212,225,263,275);
rectangle(337,225,388,275);
line(237,225,237,275);
line(212,250,263,250);
line(362,225,362,275);
line(337,250,388,250);

circle(300,165,25);

setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL, GREEN);
floodfill(210,210, BLACK);
setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL, WHITE);
floodfill(300,165, BLACK);
setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL, BROWN);
floodfill(300,125, BLACK);
/*int i,j=0,k=0;
//delay(1000);
setttextstyle(3,0,3);
setcolor(RED);
outtextxy(250,350,"DEMONSTRATION OF SEGMENTATION");
setcolor(0);
//MONITOR
rectangle(140,110,220,210);
rectangle(130,100,230,220);
line(165,220,145,250);

```

```
line(195,220,215,250);
ellipse(180,250,130,50,45,15);
line(120,90,120,210);
line(120,210,130,220);
line(120,90,220,90);
line(220,90,230,100);
setfillstyle(1,7);
floodfill(131,101,0);
setfillstyle(1,7);
floodfill(121,91,0);
line(120,90,130,100);
setfillstyle(1,7);
floodfill(166,222,0);

getch();
//delay(1100);
//CABINET
setfillstyle(1,7);
bar3d(350,90,280,250,7,1);
setfillstyle(1,8);
floodfill(345,87,0);
setfillstyle(1,8);
floodfill(353,235,0);
getch();
//delay(1000);
//CD ROM
setcolor(0);
line(280,100,350,100);
line(280,110,350,110);
setfillstyle(1,8);
floodfill(281,101,0);
setfillstyle(1, GREEN);
fillellipse(340,105,4,4);
ellipse(340,105,100,90,5,5);

//delay(1000);
getch();
//FLOPPY

setfillstyle(1,7);
floodfill(291,151,0);
rectangle(290,150,335,158);
setfillstyle(1,8);
floodfill(291,151,0);

//delay(1000);
getch();
//RESET BUTTON
setfillstyle(1, RED);
fillellipse(310,180,4,4);
ellipse(310,180,100,90,3,5);
```

```
//delay(1000);
getch();
//POWER BUTTON
setfillstyle(1,YELLOW);
fillellipse(310,200,4,4);
ellipse(310,200,100,90,7,8);
circle(310,200,8);

//MONITOR CONNECTOR
//delay(1000);
getch();
setcolor(0);
line(230,210,250,200);
line(231,211,251,201);
line(232,212,252,202);

line(250,200,280,180);
line(251,201,280,181);
line(252,202,280,182);

setcolor(0);
//delay(1000);
getch();
//KEYBOARD
k=0;
for(i=0;i<7;i++)
{
line(106+k,280+j,258+k,280+j);
j+=8;
k+=3;
}

j=0;
for(i=0;i<20;i++)
{
line(106+j,280,125+j,328);
j+=8;
}
line(106,280,106,290);
line(106,290,125,338);
line(277,328,277,338);
line(125,338,277,338);
setfillstyle(1,7);
floodfill(126,329,0);
line(125,328,125,338);

//delay(1000);
```

```
getch();
//KEYBOARD CONNECTOR
line(210,280,280,230);
line(211,281,281,231);
line(250,250,280,230);

//delay(1000);
getch();
//MOUSE
setfillstyle(1,7);
fillellipse(300,300,9,15);
ellipse(300,300,100,90,10,18);

//delay(1000);
getch();
line(300,285,270,260);
line(301,286,271,261);
line(302,287,272,262);

line(270,260,245,250);
line(271,261,246,251);
line(272,262,247,252);

line(245,250,280,205);
line(246,251,280,206);
line(247,252,280,207);

//display on screen
settextstyle(3,0,1);
setcolor(0);
outtextxy(142,150,"CG PROJECT");
outtextxy(142,165,"By:uub1970");
//outtextxy(165,175,"Usha");
for(i=0;i<=5;i++)
{ delay(1000);
  if(i%2==0)
  {
    setfillstyle(1,11);
    floodfill(141,111,0);
  }
  else
  {
    setfillstyle(1,14);
    floodfill(141,111,0);
  }
}*/

}
void mul(float a[10][10],float d[10][10])
{
```

```

char k1[4],l1[4],m1[4];
int i,j,k,xc,yc,zc;
float c[10][10];
for(i=0;i<1;i++)
    {
        for(j=0;j<4;j++)
            {
                c[i][j]=0;
                for(k=0;k<4;k++)
                    c[i][j]+=a[i][k]*d[k][j];
            }
    }
xc=c[0][0],yc=c[0][1],zc=c[0][2];
outtextxy(570,100,"x=");
outtextxy(570,120,"y=");
outtextxy(570,140,"z=");
    sprintf(k1,"%d", (xc-MIN_X));
outtextxy(600,100,k1);
    sprintf(l1,"%d", (yc-MIN_Y));
outtextxy(600,120,l1);
    sprintf(m1,"%d", (zc-100));
outtextxy(600,140,m1);
if(xc>MIN_X&&yc>MIN_Y&&xc<MAX_X&&yc<MAX_Y)
    {
        putpixel(xc,yc,RED);
        putpixel(xc+1,yc+1,RED);
        putpixel(xc,yc+1,RED);
        putpixel(xc+1,yc,RED);
    }
    else
        outtextxy(150,316,"sorry! pixel is outside the
boundary");
}

void t3d()
{
char
*xs,*ys,*zs,*chs,*txs,*tys,*tzs,*sxs,*sys,*szs,*angs;

float a[10][10],d[10][10],c[9][9];
int tx,ty,tz,sx,sy,sz,ch;
    int x,y,z,ang,i;
    float th;
        xs=readline("Enter x cordinate:(0-525) ");
        x=atoi(xs);
        ys=readline("Enter y cordinate:(0-290) ");
        y=atoi(ys);
        zs=readline("Enter z cordinate:(0-300) ");
        z=atoi(zs);
        x=x+MIN_X;
        y=y+MIN_Y;

```

```

        z=z+100;
        putpixel(x,y,BLUE);
        putpixel(x+1,y+1,BLUE);
        putpixel(x+1,y,BLUE);
        putpixel(x,y+1,BLUE);
        d[0][0]=x,d[0][1]=y,d[0][2]=z,d[0][3]=1;
4.Yrotate 5.Xrotate");
        ch=atoi(chs);
        switch(ch)
        {

            case 1:
                txs=readline("Enter tx: ");
                tx=atoi(txs);
                tys=readline("Enter ty ");
                ty=atoi(tys);
                tzs=readline("Enter tz: ");
                tz=atoi(tzs);
                a[0][0]=a[1][1]=a[2][2]=a[3][3]=1;
                a[3][0]=tx;a[3][1]=ty;a[3][2]=tz;

                a[0][1]=a[0][2]=a[0][3]=a[1][0]=a[1][2]=a[1][3]=a[2]
[0]=a[2][1]=a[2][3]=0;
                mul(d,a);

                break;

            case 2:sxs=readline("Enter sx: ");
                sx=atoi(sxs);
                sys=readline("Enter sy ");
                sy=atoi(sys);
                szs=readline("Enter sz: ");
                sz=atoi(szs);
                a[0][0]=sx;a[1][1]=sy;
                a[2][2]=sz;a[3][3]=1;

                a[0][1]=a[0][2]=a[0][3]=a[1][0]=a[1][2]=a[1][3]=a[2]
[0]=a[2][1]=a[2][3]=a[3][0]=a[3][1]=a[3][2]=0;
                mul(d,a);

                break;
            case 3:
                angs=readline("enter rotatinal angle about
z");

                ang=atoi(angs);

                th=(3.142*ang)/180;
                a[0][0]=a[1][1]=cos(th);

```

```

        a[0][2]=a[1][2]=a[0][3]=a[1][3]=a[2][1]=a[2][0]=a[3]
[0]=a[3][1]=a[3][2]=a[2][3]=0;
        a[3][3]=a[2][2]=1;
        a[0][1]=sin(th);a[1][0]=-sin(th);
        mul(d,a);

        break;
        case 4:
            angs=readline("enter rotatinal angle
about y");
            ang=atoi(angs);

            th=(3.142*ang)/180;
            a[1][1]=a[3][3]=1;

            a[0][1]=a[0][3]=a[1][0]=a[1][2]=a[1][3]=a[2][1]=a[2]
[3]=a[3][0]=a[3][1]=a[3][2]=0;
            a[0][0]=a[2][2]=cos(th);
            a[2][0]=sin(th);
            a[0][2]=-sin(th);
            mul(d,a);

            break;
            case 5:
                angs=readline("enter rotatinal angle
about x");
                ang=atoi(angs);
                th=(3.142*ang)/180;
                a[0][0]=a[3][3]=1;
                a[1][1]=a[2][2]=cos(th);
                a[1][2]=sin(th);a[2][1]=-sin(th);

                a[0][1]=a[0][2]=a[0][3]=a[1][0]=a[1][3]=a[2][0]=a[2]
[3]=a[3][0]=a[3][1]=a[3][2]=0;
                mul(d,a);

                break;
            default:exit(0);
        }

    }

void translate()
{
    char *name;
    int tx,ty;
    setcolor(Current_Color);
    rectangle(MIN_X,MIN_Y,MAX_X,MAX_Y);
    ShowStatus("Draw rectangle to translate");
    drawrectangle();
}

```

```

    name=readline("Enter the translation factor tx: ");
    tx=atoi(name);
    name=readline("Enter the translation factor ty: ");
    ty=atoi(name);
    setcolor(WHITE);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,WHITE);
    bar(a,b,c,d);
    if(c+tx >MAX_X)          c=MAX_X;
    else if(c+tx < MIN_Y)    c=MIN_Y;
    else                     c=c+tx;

    if(d+ty >MAX_Y)          d=MAX_Y;
    else if(d+ty <MIN_Y)    d=MIN_Y;
    else                     d=d+ty;

    if(a+tx <MIN_X)          a=MIN_X;
    else if( a+tx >MAX_X)    a=MAX_X;
    else                     a=a+tx;

    if( b+ty<MIN_Y)          b=MIN_Y;
    else if(b+ty >MAX_Y)    b=MAX_Y;
    else                     b=b+ty;

    setcolor(Current_Color);
    if(Current_Pattern!=EMPTY_FILL)
        setfillstyle(Current_Pattern,Current_Color);
    bar(a,b,c,d);
    rectangle(a,b,c,d);
}

void insert(int x,int y,struct Node** last)
{
    struct Node* p;
    p=(struct Node*)malloc(sizeof(struct Node));
    if(p==NULL)
    {
        closegraph();
        fprintf(stderr,"\ninsert:Out of memory.\n");
        exit(2);
    }
    p->x=x;
    p->y=y;
    p->next=NULL;
    (*last)->next=p;
    *last=(*last)->next;
}

void floodfill4(int x,int y,int oldclr,int newclr)
{
    struct Node* first,*last,*tmp;
    struct Node* p,*q;

```

```
    first=(struct Node*)malloc(sizeof(struct Node));
    if(first==NULL)
    {
        closegraph();
        fprintf(stderr,"floodfill4: Out of memory.\n");
        exit(2);
    }
    if(oldclr==newclr)
    {
        free(first);
        return;
    }

    //Create a node and store the seed there.
    first->x=x;
    first->y=y;
    first->next=NULL;
    last=first;

    //Use a linked list of adjacent nodes for filling
    while(first!=NULL)
    {
        putpixel(x,y,newclr);
        if(getpixel(x,y-1)==oldclr)
        {
            putpixel(x,y-1,newclr);
            insert(x,y-1,&last); //insert at the end
        }
        if(getpixel(x,y+1)==oldclr)
        {
            putpixel(x,y+1,newclr);
            insert(x,y+1,&last); //insert at the end
        }
        if(getpixel(x-1,y)==oldclr)
        {
            putpixel(x-1,y,newclr);
            insert(x-1,y,&last); //insert at the end
        }
        if(getpixel(x+1,y)==oldclr)
        {
            putpixel(x+1,y,newclr);
            insert(x+1,y,&last); //insert at the end
        }
    }

    //This pixel is done .try the next node in the list

    tmp=first;
    first=first->next;
    x=first->x;
    y=first->y;
    free(tmp);
```

```
    }
    for(p=first;p!=NULL;p=q)
    {
        q=p->next;
        free(p);
    }
}

void fillcolor()
{
    unsigned oldcolor;
    int x=mousex;
    int y=mousey;
    oldcolor=getpixel(mousex,mousey);
    hidemouse();
    floodfill4(x,y,oldcolor,Current_Color);
    showmouse();
}

void myl(int x,int y,float theta)
{
    line((int)(x+70*sqrt(2)*cos(theta)),(int)(y+70*sqrt(2)*sin(theta)),(int)(x+70*sqrt(2)*cos(theta+M_PI_2)),(int)(y+70*sqrt(2)*sin(theta+M_PI_2)));
    circle(x,y,70);
}

void rotate_line()
{
    float theta=0;
    int i,j;
    clear();
    ShowStatus("Press ESC to terminate");
    while(1)
    {
        if(kbhit())
            if(getch()==27)
            {
                clear();
                return;
            }
        setcolor(BLACK);
        myl(360,249,theta);
        delay(100);
        setcolor(WHITE);
        myl(360,249,theta);

        theta+=M_PI_2/10;
    }
}
```

```
    }
}

extern void draw_button_border(int);
extern void undraw_button_border(int);

typedef unsigned int outcode;
enum
{
    top=0x1,bottom=0x2,right=0x4,left=0x8
};

outcode compcode(int x,int y,int xmin,int ymin,int
xmax,int ymax)
{
    outcode code=0;
    if(y>ymax) code|=top;
    if(y<ymin) code|=bottom;
    if(x>xmax) code|=right;
    if(x<xmin) code|=left;
    return code;
}

int x2,y2,x3,y3;

void CohenSutherlandLine(int x0,int y0,int x1,int y1,int
xmin,int ymin,int xmax,int ymax)
{
    outcode outcodeout,outcode0,outcode1;
    int
    accept=0,done=1,x,y,umin=MIN_X+100,vmin=MIN_Y+50,umax=MAX
_X-100,vmax=MAX_Y-50;
    float m;

    outcode0=compcode(x0,y0,xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax);
    outcode1=compcode(x1,y1,xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax);
    while(done)
    {
        if(!(outcode0|outcode1))
        {
            accept=1;
            done=0;
        }
        else if(outcode0&outcode1)
            done=0;
        else
        {
            outcodeout=outcode0?outcode0:outcode1;
            m=(y1-y0)/(float)(x1-x0);

            if(outcodeout&top)
```

```
{
    x=x0+(ymax-y0)/m;
    y=ymax;
}
else if(outcodeout&bottom)
{
    x=x0+(ymin-y0)/m;
    y=ymin;
}
else if(outcodeout&right)
{
    y=y0+(xmax-x0)*m;
    x=xmax;
}
else
{
    y=y0+(xmin-x0)*m;
    x=xmin;
}
if(outcodeout==outcode0)
{
    x0=x; y0=y;
    outcode0=comPCODE(x0,y0,xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax);
}
else
{
    x1=x; y1=y;
    outcode1=comPCODE(x1,y1,xmin,ymin,xmax,ymax);
}
}
hidemouse();
clear();
if(accept)
{
    setcolor(BLACK);
    outtextxy(110,80,"Clipped line in the window");
    rectangle(x3,y3,x2,y2);
    setcolor(Current_Color);
    bline(x0,y0,x1,y1);
    ClearStatus();
    ShowStatus("Right click to view Clipped line in
Viewport");
    getxy();
    while(!RightButtonPressed) getxy();

    x0=(float)(x0-xmin)*(umax-umin)/(xmax-xmin)+umin;
    x1=(float)(x1-xmin)*(umax-umin)/(xmax-xmin)+umin;
    y0=(float)(y0-ymin)*(vmax-vmin)/(ymax-ymin)+vmin;
    y1=(float)(y1-ymin)*(vmax-vmin)/(ymax-ymin)+vmin;
```

```
        clear();
        setcolor(BLACK);
        outtextxy(110,80,"Clipped line in viewport");
        rectangle(umin,vmin,umax,vmax);
        setcolor(Current_Color);
        bline(x0,y0,x1,y1);
    } // if line within the region
    showmouse();
    setcolor(Current_Color);
}

void lineclipping()
{
    int x,y,current_x,current_y,tx,ty,b,color;
    int x0,y0,x1,y1;
    R=1;
    clear();
    showmouse();
    getxy();
    x=mousex;y=mousey;
    disp_coord();
    if(LeftButtonPressed)
    {
        while(LeftButtonPressed)
        {
            getxy();disp_coord();
            if(prevx==mousex&&prevy==mousey)
                continue;
            hidemouse();
            putback();
            showmouse();
            getxy();
            hidemouse();
            bline(x,y,mousex,mousey);
            showmouse();
            delay(10);
        }
        x0=x;y0=y;x1=mousex;y1=mousey;
        ClearStatus(); ShowStatus("Draw the Clipping
Window");
        getxy();
        while(!LeftButtonPressed)
        {
            getxy();
            disp_coord();
        }
        hidemouse();
        setcolor(15-BLACK);
        setwritemode(XOR_PUT);
        x=mousex;
        y=mousey;
```

```

        while (LeftButtonPressed)
        {
            setlinestyle(3,1,1);
            disp_coord();
            current_x=mousex;
            current_y=mousey;
            while(current_x==mousex && current_y==mousey)
                getxy();
            rectangle(x,y,current_x,current_y);
            rectangle(x,y,mousex,mousey);
        }
        setlinestyle(0,1,1);
        setwritemode(COPY_PUT);
        setcolor(Current_Color);
        ClearStatus();
        showmouse();
        x3=mousex, y3=mousey, x2=x, y2=y;
        if(x2>x3)
            current_x=x2,x2=x3,x3=current_x;
        if(y2>y3)
            current_y=y2,y2=y3,y3=current_y;
        CohenSutherlandLine(x0,y0,x1,y1,x2,y2,x3,y3);
        t=0;
        draw_button_border(Current_Button);
        undraw_button_border(Prev_Button);
        Current_Button=Prev_Button;
    }//if left button
}

void icons(int minx,int miny,int maxx,int maxy,int
status)
{
    int up=WHITE,down=DARKGRAY; // ICON is used to draw
buttons creating a
    int color=getcolor();// 3d effect with top and left
drawn in darkgray
    if(status==0)// bottom and right drawn in white ,color
gets swapped
    {
        // when a button is pressed indicating as
though it has
        up=DARKGRAY;// gone inside
        down=WHITE;
    }
    setcolor(up);
    line(minx,miny,maxx,miny);
    line(minx,miny,minx,maxy);
    setcolor(down);
    line(minx,maxy,maxx,maxy);
    line(maxx,maxy,maxx,miny);
    setcolor(color);
}

```

```
void init_button(int no,int xmin,int ymin,int xwidth,int
ywidth,char* desc)
{
    int ygap=4;          //the vertical gap between two
buttons
    buttons[no].xmin=xmin;
    buttons[no].ymin=ymin;
    buttons[no].xmax=xmin+xwidth;
    buttons[no].ymax=ymin+ywidth-ygap;
    buttons[no].desc=(char
*)malloc(strlen(desc)+1); //string for ShowStatus()
    if(buttons[no].desc==NULL)
    {
        cleardevice();
        printf("\n No MEMORY ");
    }
    strcpy(buttons[no].desc,desc);
}

void draw_button_border(int no)//this creates the "not-
pressed-normal" effect
{
    hidemouse();          //hiding mouse using dos
interrupt

    icons(buttons[no].xmin,buttons[no].ymin,buttons[no].xmax,
buttons[no].ymax,1);

    icons(buttons[no].xmin+1,buttons[no].ymin+1,buttons[no].x
max-1,buttons[no].ymax-1,1);
    showmouse();
}

void undraw_button_border(int no)//this creates the
"pressed" effect
{
    hidemouse();//actually to avoid graying effect along
the edges

    icons(buttons[no].xmin,buttons[no].ymin,buttons[no].xmax,
buttons[no].ymax,0);

    icons(buttons[no].xmin+1,buttons[no].ymin+1,buttons[no].x
max-1,buttons[no].ymax-1,0);
    showmouse();
}

void init_color_button(int color,int xmin,int ymin,int
xwidth,int ywidth)
```

```
{          //this actually inits various fields of
struct color-button
    int xgap=4; //the hori-gap between 2 color buttons
    colorbuttons[color].xmin=xmin;
    colorbuttons[color].xmax=xmin+xwidth-xgap;
    colorbuttons[color].ymin=ymin;
    colorbuttons[color].ymax=ymin+ywidth;
    colorbuttons[color].color=color;
}

// draws color buttons that are in struct colorbuttons

void draw_color_button_border(int no)
{
    int color=getcolor();
    setcolor(BLACK);

    rectangle(colorbuttons[no].xmin+1,colorbuttons[no].ymin+1
,colorbuttons[no].xmax-1,colorbuttons[no].ymax-1);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,no);

    floodfill(colorbuttons[no].xmin+3,colorbuttons[no].ymin+3
,BLACK);
    setcolor(color);
}

void init() //this fn initializes the various fields of
the struct button
{          //this is done iteratively for all buttons of
the struct-array
    int
x1=10+10,y1=MIN_Y+12,x2=54,y2=MAX_Y+47,ywidth=30,xwidth=3
0;
    int butt=0,i,j;
    setcolor(BROWN);

    //icon panel
    New_icon(x1,y1+1);
    init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"New File"); //of
struct button
    draw_button_border(butt++);

    Save_icon(x2,y1);
    init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Save File");
    draw_button_border(butt++);
    y1+=ywidth;

    Open_icon(x1,y1);
    init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Load File");
    draw_button_border(butt++);
```

```
Clear_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Clear File");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

Line_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Line Drawing
Tool");
draw_button_border(butt++);

Rectangle_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Rectangle
Drawing Tool");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

Circle_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Circle Drawing
Tool");
draw_button_border(butt++);

Ellipse_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Ellipse Drawing
Tool");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

Spiral_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Spiral Drawing
Tool");
draw_button_border(butt++);

Clip_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Line Clipper");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

Rot_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Rotating line
around circle tangentially");
draw_button_border(butt++);

Wheel_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Rotating
Wheel");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;
```

```
Seg_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"Segmentation");
draw_button_border(butt++);

hr_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"DRAW HRMITE
CURVE ");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

bz_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"DRAW BEZIER
CURVE");
draw_button_border(butt++);

t3d_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"3D ROTATION ");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

Translate_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"TRANSLATE
RECTANGLE");
draw_button_border(butt++);
//y1+=ywidth;

fl_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"FILL A COLOR");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

scale_icon(x1,y1);
init_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"SCALING
RECTANGLE");
draw_button_border(butt++);

Rotate_icon(x2,y1);
init_button(butt,x2,y1,xwidth,ywidth,"ROTATING A
RECTANGLE");
draw_button_border(butt++);
y1+=ywidth;

//now, the color buttons
butt=0;
x1=MIN_X+75;
y1=MAX_Y+28;
```

```

    xwidth=30;ywidth=15;
    for(i=0;i<8;i++)          //iteratively init the col-but
structure
    {                          //init color button is very
similar to init_button
        init_color_button(butt,x1,y1,xwidth,ywidth);
        draw_color_button_border(butt++);
        init_color_button(butt,x1,y2,xwidth,ywidth);
        draw_color_button_border(butt++);
        x1=x1+xwidth;
    }
    setcolor(Current_Color); }
void dispfile() //display and updates filename in case of
load/save,etc
{
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
    bar(260,MIN_Y-30,379,MIN_Y-6);
    icons(260,MIN_Y-30,379,MIN_Y-6,1);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
    bar(MAX_X-15+8,4,MAX_X+1+8,15-2);
    icons(MAX_X-15+8,4,MAX_X+1+8,15-2,1);
    icons(MAX_X-14+8,5,MAX_X+8,15-3,1);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    settextstyle(DEFAULT_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,0);
    outtextxy(MAX_X-10+8,4,"x"); // exits on clicking
    outtextxy((getmaxx()-
textwidth(filename))/2,48,filename);
}

/*                          BASIC OPERATIONS
*/

int check_mouse_on(int minx,int miny,int maxx,int
maxy)//is mouse is on area
{
//defined by boundary?
    if(mousex<minx || mousex>maxx || mousey<miny ||
mousey>maxy)
        return 0;
    return 1;
}

int check_if_color()
{
    int i=0;
    for(i=0;i<MAX_COLOR;i++)
    {

```

```

if(check_mouse_on(colorbuttons[i].xmin,colorbuttons[i].ym
in,colorbuttons[i].xmax,colorbuttons[i].ymax))
{
    Current_Color=colorbuttons[i].color;
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,Current_Color);
    bar(MIN_X+20,MAX_Y+35,MIN_X+44,MAX_Y+50);
    setcolor(BLACK);
    rectangle(MIN_X+20,MAX_Y+35,MIN_X+44,MAX_Y+50);
    setcolor(Current_Color);
    return 1;
}
}
return 0;
}
int check_if_button_pressed()
{
    int ret_value=-1,color;
    int i;
    char ch;
    for(i=0;i<MAX_BUTTONS;++i)
    {

if(check_mouse_on(buttons[i].xmin,buttons[i].ymin,buttons
[i].xmax,buttons[i].ymax))
    {
        if(LeftButtonPressed && i!=Current_Button) //check
which button
        {
            // if not
current button
            ret_value=i;                //change current
button = i
            draw_button_border(Current_Button);
            Prev_Button=Current_Button;
            Current_Button=i;
            undraw_button_border(Current_Button);
            switch(Current_Button)
            {
                case NEW :
                    hidemouse();
                    if(!saved)
                    {
                        ShowStatus("Save Changes (Y or N) ? ");
                        ch=getch();
                        if(ch=='y' || ch=='Y')
                            save();
                    }
                    strcpy(filename,"Untitled");
                    dispfile();
                    clear();
                    draw_button_border(Current_Button);

```

```
        undraw_button_border(Prev_Button);
        Current_Button=Prev_Button;
        showmouse();
        break;

    case CLEAR :
        hidemouse();
        clear();
        draw_button_border(Current_Button);
        undraw_button_border(Prev_Button);
        Current_Button=Prev_Button;
        showmouse();
        break;

    case LOAD:
        hidemouse();
        load();
        draw_button_border(Current_Button);
        undraw_button_border(Prev_Button);
        Current_Button=Prev_Button;
        showmouse();
        break;

    case SAVE:
        hidemouse();
        save();
        draw_button_border(Current_Button);
        undraw_button_border(Prev_Button);
        Current_Button=Prev_Button;
        showmouse();
        break;

    case CLIP_OP:
        clear();
        break;
    case TRANS_OP:
        clear();
    }
}
if(prevx!=mousex||prevy!=mousey)
    ShowStatus(buttons[i].desc);
return ret_value;
} //check on which button
} //for all button
ClearStatus();
return ret_value;
}

void tools()
{
```

```
restrictmouse(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-2,MAX_Y-2);
hidemouse();
switch(Current_Button)
{
    case 4 :
    case 5 :
    case 6 :
    case 7 :
    case 13:
    case 14:
    case 8 : rubberband();
            break;

    case 9 : //freehand();
            lineclipping();
            break;

    case 10: //lineclipping();
            rotate_line();
            break;

    case 11: //drawtext();
            Wheel();
            break;

    case 12: //rotate_line();
            seg();
            break;

    case 15: //restrictmouse(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-
10,MAX_Y-10);
            //brush();
            t3d();
            break;

    case 17: //clearout();
            fillcolor();
            break;

    case 16:translate();
//clearin();
            break;

    case 18: //seg();
            scale();
            break;

    case 19: rotate();
            break;
    /*
```

```
        case 22:// t3d();
            break;
    case 23:
        //fillcolor();
        break;
        */
    }
    showmouse();
    restrictmouse(0,0,639,479);
}
void rubberband()
{
    int x,y,xe,ye,tx,ty,b,r1,r2;
    R=1;
    showmouse();
    getxy();
    x=mousex;y=mousey;
    disp_coord();
    if(LeftButtonPressed)
    {
        while(LeftButtonPressed)
        {
            getxy();disp_coord();
            if(prevx==mousex&&prevy==mousey)
                continue;
            hidemouse();
            putback();
            showmouse();
            getxy();
            hidemouse();
            switch(Current_Button)
            {
                case 4: bline(x,y,mousex,mousey);
                    break;

                case 5: brectangle(x,y,mousex,mousey);
                    break;

                case 6: bcircle(x,y,abs(x-mousex)<abs(y-
mousey)?abs(y-mousey):abs(x-mousex));
                    break;

                case 7: r1=abs(x-mousex),r2=abs(y-mousey);
                    if(r1!=0&&r2!=0) //else floating point
error
                        bellipse(x,y,abs(x-mousex),abs(y-
mousey));
                    break;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```
        case 8: spiral(x,y,abs(x-mousex)<abs(y-
mousey)?abs(y-mousey):abs(x-mousex),1,50);
            break;
        case 13:hrcurve(x,y,mousex,mousey);
            break;
        case 14:bzcurve(x,y,mousex,mousey);

            break;

    }
    showmouse();
    delay(10);
} //while left button
t=0;
} //if left button
}

void Wheel()
{
    char ch;
    int x,y,s;
    float theta=0;
    int i,j,f,b;
    // flushall();
    clear();
    ShowStatus("Press ESC to terminate");
    getxy();
    hidemouse();
    while(!LeftButtonPressed)
    {
        getxy();
        for(i=153;i<=573;i+=8)
        {
            if(kbhit())
                if(getch()==27)
                {
                    clear();
                    showmouse();
                    return;
                }
            setcolor(BLACK);
            myw(i,230,theta);
            delay(130);
            setcolor(WHITE);
            myw(i,230,theta);
            theta+=M_PI/10;
        }
        for(i=573;i>=153;i-=8)
        {
            if(kbhit())
```

```
        if (getch() == 27)
        {
            clear();
            showmouse();
            return;
        }
        setcolor(BLACK);
        myw(i, 230, theta);
        delay(130);
        setcolor(WHITE);
        myw(i, 230, theta);
        theta -= M_PI/10;
    }
}
clear();
showmouse();
}

void scale()
{
    char *name;
    float sx, sy;
    setcolor(Current_Color);
    rectangle(MIN_X, MIN_Y, MAX_X, MAX_Y);
    ShowStatus("Draw rectangle to scale");
    drawrectangle();

    name = readline("Enter the scaling factor sx: ");
    sx = atof(name);
    name = readline("Enter the scaling factor sy: ");
    sy = atof(name);

    setcolor(WHITE);
    setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL, WHITE);
    bar(a, b, c, d);

    c = (float)(c - a) * sx + (float)a;
    d = (float)(d - b) * sy + (float)b;
    if (c >= MAX_X)        c = MAX_X - 1;

    if (d >= MAX_Y)        d = MAX_Y - 1;

    setcolor(Current_Color);
    if (Current_Pattern != EMPTY_FILL)
        setfillstyle(Current_Pattern, Current_Color);
    bar(a, b, c, d);
    rectangle(a, b, c, d);
}

void drawrectangle()
{

```

```
int color=15-Current_Color;
int x,y;
setcolor(color);
setwritemode(XOR_PUT);

x=mousex;
y=mousey;

while (LeftButtonPressed)
{
    disp_coord();
    rectangle(x,y,mousex,mousey);
    getxy();
    rectangle(x,y,mousex,mousey);
}
setwritemode(COPY_PUT);
setcolor(Current_Color);

a=x, b=y, c=mousex, d=mousey;

if(Current_Pattern==EMPTY_FILL)
    rectangle(x,y,mousex,mousey);
else
{
    setfillstyle(Current_Pattern,Current_Color);
    bar(x,y,mousex,mousey);
}
}

void main()
{
    int gd=DETECT,gm;
    initgraph(&gd,&gm,"C:\\tc\\bgi");
    if(!initmouse())
    {
        outtextxy(250,230,"Mouse not present");
        getch();
        exit(0);
    }
    wel();
    cleardevice();
    frame();// To create window
    startmouse((MIN_X+MAX_X)/2,(MIN_Y+MAX_Y)/2);
    showmouse();
    init(); // To display all icons
    undraw_button_border(Current_Button);
    dispfile();
    while(1)
    {
        tme();
    }
}
```

```

        getxy();
        if(!check_mouse_on(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-2,MAX_Y-
2))
        {
            setfillstyle(SOLID_FILL,LIGHTGRAY);
            bar(487,462,522,472);           //refresh display
            bar(555,462,585,472);
        }
        else disp_coord();
        if(LeftButtonPressed)
        {
            if(check_if_button_pressed())>=0) ;
            else if(check_if_color())
                ClearStatus();
            else if(check_mouse_on(MIN_X+2,MIN_Y+2,MAX_X-
2,MAX_Y-2))
            {
                ClearStatus();
                saved=0;
                tools();
            }
            else check_if_exit();
        }
        else check_if_button_pressed();
    }
}
//                to display exiting page

void check_if_exit()//is mouse on exit area?
{ char ch;
struct dosdate_t d;
struct dostime_t t;
    if((check_mouse_on(MAX_X-15+1+8,4,MAX_X-1+8,15-
3))&&LeftButtonPressed)
    {
        hidemouse();
        icons(MAX_X-15+8,4,MAX_X-1+8,15-3,0);
        icons(MAX_X-14+8,4,MAX_X+8,15-3,0);
        ClearStatus();
        ShowStatus("Save and exit(Y or N)?");
        ch=getch();
        if(ch=='y' || ch=='Y')
        {
            save();
        }
        clearviewport();
        cleardevice();
        settextstyle(8,0,4);
        setcolor(5);
        outtextxy(50,100,"\n");
        outtextxy(50,300,"\n");
    }
}

```

```
    setcolor(RED);
    outtextxy(100,25,"\n");
    outtextxy(100,375,"\n");
    rectangle(1,1,637,477);
    rectangle(3,3,635,475);

    setcolor(BLUE);
    outtextxy(190,200,"THANK YOU!!!!");
    setcolor(9);
    outtextxy(189,201,"THANK YOU!!!!");
    settextstyle(0,0,0);
    setcolor(12);

    _dos_getdate(&d);
    printf(" %d-%d-%d ", d.day,d.month,d.year);

    _dos_gettime(&t);
    printf(" %2d:%02d:%02d\n", t.hour, t.minute,t.second);
    outtextxy(430,450,"NOW PRESS ANY KEY TO EXIT");
    settextstyle(DEFAULT_FONT,HORIZ_DIR,0);
    getch(); exit(0);
}
}
```

5. SAMPLE OUTPUT

CONCLUSION

We have attempted to design and implement a paint editor using C/C++, which supports enormous flexibility in the design and the use of graphics functions. The presence of many in-built classes and methods take care of many of the functionalities and reduce the job of coding as well as makes the implementation simpler.

The project was started with the designing phase in which we figured the requirements needed, the layout design, then comes the detail designing of each function after which, was the testing and debugging stage.

We have tried to implement the project making it as user-friendly and error free as possible.

In future enhancement, the following features are addressed.

The most obvious enhancement that we see is, support for the standard image formats such as BMP, JPEG, GIF etc. This would allow the editor to open image documents stored in these standard formats. We would also like to support saving of our documents in these formats so that the editor is compatible with all the standard graphics editors.

Another feature we would like to incorporate is to provide a way for the user to store and open documents in directories other than the current directory. We would like to provide the user with a simple way to traverse the directory structure for file operations.

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